

Deliverable D7.5 Retrospective assessment of national use-cases, identification of gaps, and recommendations for future Federated EGA roadmap

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1. Executive Summary

This report provides an overview of assessing national use-cases, identifying gaps, and providing recommendations for the future of the Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA). The assessment focuses on facilitating the adoption of FEGA by ELIXIR National Nodes and 1+MG National Mirror Groups. It presents insights gained from engagement with twelve ELIXIR CONVERGE WP7 partner nodes, twelve nodes involved in other European data sharing initiatives like the European Genome Data Infrastructure and Beyond 1 Million Genomes project, and seven nodes not currently part of these initiatives, including five nodes outside of Europe.

Several approaches were taken to address the objectives, including national node use case surveys, individual node check-in meetings, self-assessments against the FEGA Maturity Model, and outreach activities. The node use case surveys collected information from 11 completed surveys, highlighting common data types and user profiles relevant to FEGA. The individual node check-in meetings provided a platform for discussions between Central EGA and ten nodes, covering FEGA node status, challenges, and future plans. Aggregated results from these meetings are included in the report. Nodes were also encouraged to perform self-assessments against the FEGA Maturity Model, and additional feedback was provided through ad hoc meetings. Various outreach activities were coordinated to understand national use cases, identify gaps, and compile recommendations for future FEGA development. These activities were conducted in collaboration with CONVERGE WP7 partners, CONVERGE WP2, and external partners and projects.

The report concludes that FEGA is currently supporting the most common use cases in terms of data types and users and has captured the most common challenges. The challenges identified align with the domains in the FEGA Maturity Model, indicating that the model provides a comprehensive framework for meeting these challenges to support node development. Unique use cases and challenges identified by nodes present opportunities for FEGA to fill gaps, such as developing best practices for linking to data in other resources, forming partnerships with biobanking organisations, and promoting the value of FEGA to local governments and national healthcare systems. Overall, the report provides valuable insights into the status of FEGA adoption, identifies gaps and challenges, and offers recommendations for the future roadmap. These findings can inform the further development and expansion of FEGA to support the discovery and access of sensitive human omics and associated data for secondary use.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
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Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Yes
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	Yes
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	Yes
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	Yes
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes

Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	Yes
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No
Objectives - WP7 - Federated European Genome-phenome Archives for transnational access of COVID-19 host data.	
O7.1: Federation architecture, interfaces, and compliance tests for the Federated EGA network (Task 7.1).	Yes
O7.2: Coordination of the development of a reference implementation sufficient to create a functional Federated EGA node (Task 7.2).	Yes
O7.3: Development of phenotype metadata model to enable mapping and linkage of COVID-19 host-clinical measures across European national nodes, and robust linkage between host and viral datasets (Task 7.3).	Yes
O7.4: The development of documentation and guidelines for the operational practices of federated EGA nodes (Task 7.4).	Yes

3. Introduction

3.1 Scope

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a **retrospective assessment of national use-cases, identification of gaps, and recommendations for the future Federated EGA (FEGA) roadmap**

to facilitate adoption of **FEGA** by ELIXIR National Nodes and 1+MG National Mirror Groups. The importance of developing FEGA as a solution for supporting discovery and access of sensitive human omics and associated data consented for secondary use has been demonstrated by elevating FEGA from a WP5 use case to its own dedicated work package, WP7. Previous deliverables and milestones in WP7 included work towards understanding individual node use cases and supporting technical and operational development of the FEGA solution to meet the requirements for the first set of national FEGA nodes. As ELIXIR CONVERGE ends - and other European data sharing initiatives like the European Genome Data Infrastructure (GDI)¹ ramp up - it is timely to do a retrospective assessment of how node use cases beyond the initial few are being supported, what gaps remain, and what the future of FEGA looks like in the context of other ongoing projects. This report represents insights gained from engagement with twelve nodes who are ELIXIR CONVERGE WP7 partners, twelve nodes who are partners in either GDI or Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG) project² and seven nodes not currently part of ELIXIR CONVERGE, GDI, or B1MG including five nodes outside of Europe, representing the global reach and potential impact of FEGA.

3.2 Methodology

To address the aims of this deliverable, several approaches were taken including (details in the “Description of work” section):

1. Encouraged nodes to complete a **national node use case survey**, initially developed for ELIXIR CONVERGE D7.1³.
2. Invited nodes to participate in an **individual node check-in meeting** with Central EGA in Q1 2023. Meetings were semi-structured and covered the status of nodes setting up FEGA, challenges nodes are facing, and nodes’ future plans.
3. Encouraged nodes to complete a **self-assessment against the FEGA Maturity Model**, which was developed for ELIXIR CONVERGE D7.4⁴.
4. Attended or coordinated at least 10 **dissemination and outreach events** to understand node use cases including one event jointly run with ELIXIR CONVERGE WP2.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Node Use Case Surveys

For ELIXIR CONVERGE Deliverable D7.1 we developed a “Node Use Case Survey” to collect information about potential FEGA nodes. The survey questions were open-ended, and a copy of the survey can be viewed⁵. To-date, 26 nodes have been invited to complete the survey, and 11

¹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

² <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4893063#.ZEFK8uzMK-o>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7274357#.ZFPDy-zMLjB>

⁵ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1joOKPye9cEOo0bZEI_nAGpbs2VLG3cAmWlQ74As6sU/edit

nodes/national initiatives have completed it (42% completion rate) including 8 additional nodes since D7.1 (**Table 1**). Completed survey results were aggregated to identify common use cases and themes, how many nodes mentioned them, and what support FEAGA currently provides for them. Results are presented in the Results section and in **Table 3**.

Table 1: Status of FEAGA nodes and use case surveys. Grey = progress since D7.1 (Jun 2021).

FEAGA Node	FEAGA membership status (date joined/official)	Use case survey status
Norway	Became Official FEAGA Node (May 2022)	Invited
Germany / GHGA	Became Official FEAGA Node (Jun 2022)	Done
Sweden	Became Official FEAGA Node (Jun 2022)	Done
Finland	Became Official FEAGA Node (Sep 2022)	Done
Spain	Became Official FEAGA Node (Nov 2022)	Invited
Poland	Joined FEAGA as Observer (Sep 2021)	Done
Portugal	Joined FEAGA as Observer (May 2023)	Done
Argentina	Interested in joining FEAGA	Done
Australia	Interested in joining FEAGA	Done
Belgium	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Canada	Interested in joining FEAGA	Done
Czech Republic	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Denmark	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Estonia	Interested in joining FEAGA	Done
France	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Greece	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Hungary	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Ireland	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Italy	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited
Luxembourg	Interested in joining FEAGA	Done
Mexico	Interested in joining FEAGA	Invited

The Netherlands	Interested in joining FEGA	Done
Romania	Interested in joining FEGA	Not yet invited
Serbia	Interested in joining FEGA	Invited
Slovenia	Interested in joining FEGA	Invited
South Africa / Africa	Interested in joining FEGA	Invited
Switzerland	Interested in joining FEGA	In progress
The United Kingdom	Interested in joining FEGA	Invited

4.2 Node Check-in Meetings

From January to April 2023, ten individual node check-in meetings were held between Central EGA and Australia, Canada, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, The Netherlands, Portugal, Slovenia, Africa, and the United Kingdom. The 45-minute meetings were semi-structured and covered topics related to FEGA node status, FEGA node challenges and plans, and questions from the node for Central EGA. Nodes were also introduced to the newly developed “Pathway to becoming a FEGA node”⁶ which outlines the steps required to become a full member of the Federated EGA network. Meetings were not recorded to encourage open discussion, and private notes were taken collaboratively by meeting participants. Aggregated results of the meetings are presented in the Results section.

4.3 Self-assessment Against the FEGA Maturity Model

As part of ELIXIR CONVERGE D7.4, the FEGA Maturity Model⁷ was developed along with a tool for doing a self-assessment against the Maturity Model⁸. Self-assessment results of six FEGA nodes (Finland, Germany, Norway, Poland, Spain, Sweden) and the two Central EGA nodes (CRG, EMBL-EBI) were presented to the community at the ELIXIR All-Hands meeting in 2022⁹. After the first round of self-assessments, additional nodes - including Australia and Portugal - shared their feedback about the Maturity Model and the self-assessment tool in ad hoc meetings. All Maturity Model feedback was incorporated into use case survey and catch-up meeting feedback to inform the Results below.

4.4 Outreach Activities to Understand Use Cases

During ELIXIR CONVERGE, multiple outreach activities were coordinated and attended by FEGA representatives to understand national node use cases, discuss gaps and challenges, and discuss future directions for FEGA. Activities were done in collaboration with CONVERGE WP7 partners, CONVERGE WP2, and external partners and projects (**Table 2**).

⁶ <https://ega-archive.github.io/FEGA-onboarding/#what-does-the-journey-look-like>

⁷ <https://inab.github.io/feqa-mm/>

⁸ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1WgvywvANIRh_OPAy8RY53xfzopFMwstG08zcg3l_OTyZQ/copy

⁹ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1asFVR4a-luoh7idQJcp3A2RP0-druX1LaXPk-r7FVsY/edit>

Table 2: Outreach activities specifically aimed at understanding national use-cases, identifying gaps, and compiling recommendations for future Federated EGA.

Activity title / event	Activity type	Date	Partners involved
“Demonstrating Federated EGA starter kit for sensitive data submission, discovery, and access” at ELIXIR AHM 2023	Q&A, Workshop	Jun 2023	WP7: EMBL-EBI, ES, FI, NO, PT
“The EGA and Beacon: human genomics data services for health research cross-borders” at “Research data repositories and tools for human genomics data sharing”	Workshop	May 2022	WP7: EMBL-EBI, ES, PT
Federated EGA Onboarding Website, Maturity Model, and Training Thon Event (w/ WP2)	Contentathon	May 2023	WP7: EMBL-EBI, ES, FI, NO, PT, SE, SI Other: Poland, WP2
“EGA and FEAGA: Providing global discovery for sensitive human data” ¹⁰ at SPHN webinar series	Presentation	Apr 2023	WP7: EMBL-EBI, ES
“Federated EGA: A global network for discovery and access of sensitive human data” at 14th International Congress of Human Genetics, South Africa	Poster	Feb 2023	WP7: EMBL-EBI, ES
Hosted delegation for potential Serbian FEAGA node	Workshop	Jan 2023	WP7: EMBL-EBI, ES
FEAGA Technical and Operations Q&A Session ¹¹	Webinar	Oct 2022	WP7: DE, EMBL-EBI, ES, FI, NO, SE
“The Federated EGA: Global discovery and access for sensitive human data” at GA4GH 10th Plenary	Presentation, Panel	Sep 2022	WP7: EMBL-EBI
“Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEAGA): state of the art, Q&A and demonstration sessions” at ELIXIR AHM 2022	Q&A, Workshop	Jun 2022	WP7: DE, EMBL-EBI, ES, FI, NO, SE
“Resource considerations for establishing and operating a federated human data node” ¹² at ELIXIR AHM 2022	Poster	Jun 2022	WP7: EMBL-EBI, ES, FI, NO, SE Other: Poland

¹⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cujdD_cnb0o&ab_channel=SwissPersonalizedHealthNetwork-SPHN

¹¹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1viu7W_n_UtqKMD_HxOtQ1N5CSTFc12hCloSYbi9C5-8/edit

¹² <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1118967.1>

5. Results

5.1 Node Use Cases

Aggregated survey results are shown in **Table 3** and described below. Node counts likely under-represent the truth given that 1) the survey questions were open-ended so some nodes might not have considered all possible answers and 2) the surveys were collected over a period of years and node use cases might have changed or expanded since they answered the survey.

Data types. As expected, the most often mentioned data types that nodes are working with are currently supported by FEGA. These data types include genetic data, clinical data, phenotypic data, and biometric data and were mentioned by 11, 8, 5, and 4 nodes, respectively. Interestingly, a few nodes mentioned working with cohorts and registries, something not directly supported by FEGA but certainly within the scope of the FEGA vision. Finally, some data types were mentioned - viral, metabolomics, and proteomics - that are not directly supported by FEGA but can be supported by linking to existing archives that manage these types of data that are typically open access (e.g. ENA¹³, MetaboLights¹⁴, and PRIDE¹⁵).

Users. Researchers from both academic and clinical settings were noted by all responding nodes as one of their expected user types. This result is in line with FEGA expectations and indeed has been the main user in mind when the FEGA was envisioned. Three nodes each mentioned hospitals and biobanks as users. This result reflects the recent expansion and translation of genomics into healthcare, although this trend appears to be happening at varying rates across different local and national levels. Finally, users such as national health authorities, private industries, and sequencing centres were each mentioned by one node and represent potential users that FEGA could target more for engagement more directly in the future.

Challenges. Five main themes emerged when asking nodes what challenges they face or anticipate facing for meeting their FEGA goals: 1) Funding, sustainability, and long-term support, 2) Legal and regulatory, 3) Technical infrastructure, 4) Data Sharing and Management, and 5) Coordination. These themes nicely overlap with domains in the FEGA Maturity Model, indicating that they have been identified as needs/challenges along with a framework (*i.e.* maturity levels) to guide node development in these areas. Interestingly, a few challenges were identified by one or two nodes which are not explicitly supported by FEGA and could represent opportunities to fill gaps. First, at least one node mentioned lack of human resources in local institutions to annotate data as a challenge. This gap presents an opportunity for FEGA data annotation “best practices” or training to be developed in collaboration with specific nodes. Second, at least one node mentioned a lack of regulations for scientific biobanking of human biospecimens as a challenge. Currently FEGA is focused on supporting managing of data, not physical specimens, but this gap presents an opportunity for FEGA to form partnerships with biobanking organisations to support linking of data to samples. Finally, at least one node mentioned a lack of political commitment as a

¹³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

¹⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

¹⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/>

challenge. While not all nodes will have or need the same level of government commitment for establishing a FEAGA node, this gap presents an opportunity for FEAGA to contribute to establishing the need for and demonstrating the value of joining the FEAGA network for nodes that need it from their local governments.

Table 3: Aggregated results of three FEAGA node use case survey questions on data types, expected users, and challenges from 11 completed surveys. **NB:** Not all nodes answered each survey question.

Use Case	No. Nodes	How use case is supported by FEAGA
<i>What types of data are you working with?</i>		
Genetic data (e.g. WES, WGS, microarray, bulk and single-cell transcriptome, methylation)		Is part of the current data model
Clinical, hospital data (e.g. EHR, imaging)		Can be accepted in the current data model
Phenotypic data		Is part of the current data model
Biometric, lifestyle data, wearables		Can be accepted in the current data model
Viral data		Can be linked to other archives
Cohorts, registries		Can be represented in the current data model
Metabolomics, microbiome		Can be linked to other archives
Proteomic		Can be linked to other archives
<i>Who are your expected types of users?</i>		
Researchers (e.g. academic, clinical)		Supporting research data reuse is the main use case for FEAGA
Biobanks		Theoretically could be supported but currently lacking concrete use cases
Hospitals		Theoretically could be supported but currently lacking concrete use cases
National health authorities		Support from FEAGA is currently

		unclear
Private industries	● ○○○○ ○○	Support from FEGA is currently unclear
Sequencing centres	● ○○○○ ○○	Can be supported by FEGA currently (usually submitted data files)
<i>What challenges do you currently face or anticipate facing in the future for meeting your goals?</i>		
Funding, sustainability, & long-term support <i>“The main challenge is long-term financing.” & “Securing sustainable funding for the infrastructure.”</i>	●●●●●● ● ○○○○	Represented by the Domain 1 of the FEGA Maturity Model: “Governance, Strategy & Sustainability”
Legal and regulatory <i>“The legislative landscape is quite complex... There are many unknowns around how a human data archive would need to be set up from a legal standpoint.”</i>	●●●●●● ● ○○○○	Represented by the Domain 2 of the FEGA Maturity Model: “Legal”
Technical infrastructure <i>“The federated nature of [our national] research infrastructures sometimes make it difficult to integrate different technical platforms.”</i>	●●●●●● ○○○○○	Represented by the Domain 4 of the FEGA Maturity Model: “Technical Infrastructure”
Data Sharing and Management <i>“Linking data with EHR and other registries”</i>	●●●○○○ ○○○○○	Represented by the Domain 3 of the FEGA Maturity Model: “Data and Metadata Management”
Coordination (within nodes and across FEGA network) <i>“Lack of an effective communication or coordination structure to synergise with other national/local EGA nodes.”</i>	●●●○○○ ○○○○○	Represented by the Domains 5 & 6 of the FEGA Maturity Model: “Operations Support” and “Communications, Community Building, and Engagement”
Political commitment	●●○○○○ ○○○○○	Not currently in scope; could be included in FEGA Maturity Model Domain 1: “Governance, Strategy & Sustainability”
Human resources for data annotation	●○○○○○ ○○○○○	Not currently in scope; could be included in FEGA Maturity Model Domain 3: “Data and Metadata Management”
Regulations for banking of human biospecimens	●○○○○○ ○○○○○	Not currently in scope; inclusion in FEGA vision is unclear

5.2 Identified Gaps

In addition to gaps described above from the use case surveys, additional gaps were identified from the surveys, check-in meetings, and outreach activities.

5.2.1 Knowledge Gaps

Resources required to establish and operate a FEGA node

Desired state: Emerging nodes can understand what resources - e.g. personnel, infrastructure, funding - are required to establish and operate a FEGA node. Some nodes need this information quite early - e.g. to cost a FEGA node for a funding call - while other nodes need this information as they start to assemble FEGA staff including hiring new staff.

Current state: Resources and experiences of inaugural nodes have been gathered and shared in the FEGA Onboarding Website¹⁶, presented at the ELIXIR All-Hands in 2022¹⁷, and at different virtual meetings and webinars. Feedback from emerging nodes is that this information is helpful to provide a broad sense of required resources, but questions remain about what resources are needed to support specific mandates and how this translates to quantitative values (e.g. FTEs).

Gap: As the inaugural nodes start to operate in production, it should become easier to quantify what resources are required to run FEGA node services and infrastructure. Therefore, there is an opportunity to supplement the existing resourcing information with more specific details about required resources on an ongoing basis.

Status of FEGA progress and developments

Desired state: Anyone can view public information about the current status of FEGA, nodes, services, events, etc. in order to understand how their needs and goals can fit into the evolving FEGA ecosystem.

Current state: FEGA updates are regularly given as part of the ELIXIR Federated Human Data Community calls, although this meeting is not as accessible to non-European or non-ELIXIR partners. FEGA-related activities and progress are advertised as part of various projects like ELIXIR CONVERGE as well as from specific FEGA nodes if they have capacity, but these communications are not centralised nor well-coordinated. FEGA updates are given at the Strategic and Operations Committees, but these Committees are closed to non-FEGA partners.

Gap: There is an opportunity to develop a more centralised and coordinated FEGA communications strategy, being guided by Domain 6 of the FEGA Maturity Model (Communications, Community Building, and Engagement). The proposal should be sustainable and independent of specific project funding, and it could potentially be coordinated with the ELIXIR Training Platform.

¹⁶ <https://ega-archive.github.io/FEGA-onboarding/>

¹⁷ <https://f1000research.com/posters/11-594>

5.2.2 Implementation Gaps

Alternative options to join or connect to the FEGA Network

Desired state: Alternative FEGA node solutions that support, for example: 1) a subset of services outlined in the FEGA Collaboration Agreement, 2) a smaller or narrower set of users, or 3) an intermediate FEGA node implementation which can meet use cases while development of a fully operating FEGA node is in progress.

Current state: There is currently a well-defined path to join the FEGA Network as a full member which includes signing the FEGA Collaboration Agreement. Before signing the Collaboration Agreement, there is an option to join the FEGA Strategic and Operations Committees as Observers (non-voting members). The FEGA network has both production and testing environments, the latter of which can be used during development to test FEGA node services including communicating messages between Central EGA and FEGA nodes.

Gap: The current path to joining the FEGA Network assumes that all nodes want to become full FEGA members and will provide all FEGA services. What is lacking are alternative paths for joining or connecting to the FEGA Network with other uses in mind. Some examples include: connecting an already existing data resource to FEGA network to support data discovery, or working closely with a clinical group to share data internally before making the data more broadly discoverable after a period of time. There is an opportunity here to pilot alternative paths with emerging nodes who have expressed these alternative use cases.

Training for FEGA node staff

Desired state: High-quality, sustainable, and FAIR training for various roles required to develop and operate a FEGA node.

Current state: Currently, training for staff who are developing and operating FEGA nodes is ad hoc and unstructured. One-on-one exchanges of FEGA node staff to share technical expertise or other knowledge are coordinated through various funded projects or grants. This approach works well while few nodes are onboarding, but it is not a particularly scalable approach.

Gap: There is an opportunity here to develop materials to train FEGA node staff including what skills and expertise are needed, e.g. for developers, devops engineers, bioinformaticians, data stewards, helpdesk staff, and operations staff. This could be combined with specific training on implementing and running shared FEGA components, for example the Submitter Portal. Collaborating with groups like the ELIXIR Training Platform could provide a useful framework and support for planning and developing FEGA staff training programs.

5.3 Recommendations for the Future

- Continue to be engaged with individual nodes to ensure understanding and capturing use cases, especially to identify and pilot new use cases.
- Formalise additional pathways to joining FEGA network, for example joining as a “community node”.

- Establish strategies and mechanisms of communication and outreach to FEGA users in coordination with individual FEGA node strategies.
- Align with other developments for federated sensitive human data management across Europe (e.g. GDI, EHDS) and the world.
- Establish a framework for collaborative development and implementation of FEGA training materials which can be adapted to staff at different nodes.
- Continue to assess gaps and establish a mechanism to capture future gaps.

6. Conclusions

Based on exploring node use cases individually via surveys, meetings, and Maturity Model self-assessments and as part of joint outreach activities, FEGA has made significant progress in assessing and supporting national node use cases. A large number of resources are available to support nodes understanding their use cases and identifying potential gaps for improvement. Emerging use cases have been identified which can serve as guidance for future goals for FEGA to work towards. It will be important for FEGA and national data archives moving forward to monitor and reassess progress, adapt to changing requirements and stakeholder needs, and most importantly continue collaborating to ensure success at national, European, and global levels.

7. Impact

Work accomplished towards identifying node use cases has resulted in a number of impressive accomplishments in the past few years. The Federated EGA was officially launched in September 2022 with the first five inaugural nodes - Germany, Finland, Norway, Spain, and Sweden - signing the Federated EGA Collaboration Agreement. Two additional nodes - Poland and Portugal - joined the FEGA Strategic and Operations Committees as Observers, and another 20 potential FEGA nodes have expressed interest in joining FEGA and are currently engaged in different governance and technical steps to set up and operate a FEGA node. Finally, FEGA services for data discovery and access were demonstrated by Central EGA, FEGA Finland, and FEGA Norway using synthetic data during the ELIXIR All-Hands Meeting in 2023.

Figure 1: European (right) and world (bottom left) maps representing current FEGA node status.

8. Next Steps

- Develop a sustainability strategy for implementing continued FEGA coordination work, e.g. through the ELIXIR Federated Human Data Implementation Study (e.g. managing FEGA Committees, running meetings, coordinating across projects and partners).
- Align technical and operational developments as partners in GDI.
- Increase community engagement through the ELIXIR Federated Human Data Community, including organising a Community Day with the support of ELIXIR.
- Explore the possibility of a joint effort between the ELIXIR Federated Human Data Community and the ELIXIR Training Platform for developing and implementing FEGA-related training both for FEGA node staff and for users.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable